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Students and Teachers' Perception of Influence of Antisocial Behaviours in Public Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis: Implication for Counselling

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ABSTRACT

The study examined Students and Teachers Perception of Influence of Antisocial Behaviours in Public Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis: Implication for Counselling. The study was guided by two objectives from which two research questions and two hypotheses were derived. The study adopted a descriptive survey design with a population of 27,082 teachers and students comprising 25,077 students and 2,005 teachers in the 38 public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 728 respondents comprising 394 students and 334 teachers. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamene's formula. The multi-stage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample of the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-designed questionnaire titled "Effects of Antisocial Behaviours on Students Academic Performance in Public Senior Secondary School Questionnaire". A test of internal consistency was conducted using Cronbach Alpha method to determine the reliability of the instrument. Reliability coefficients of 0.79, and 0.81 were obtained for the various clusters of the instrument. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation statistics while the hypotheses were tested using z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed, among others, that truancy and drug abuse influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The study recommends among others that, parents and school administrators must work together to keep students' behaviour under effective control, as many of the causes of anti-social behaviour can be traced to schools, homes, and peer influence.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Antisocial Behaviours, Counselling, Influence, Students, Secondary School.

INTRODUCTION

Academic performance is one of the most significant indicators of teaching and learning in the educational systems. Academic performance is the scholastic standing of a student at any given moment which could be explained in terms of grades obtained in a subject or subjects (Mekonnen, 2018). It is the grade assigned or awarded to students after series of teaching and learning exercises usually measured by continuous assessments or examinations. As a dependent variable, Academic performance is highly influenced by many factors such as interest, motivation, home education environment, parental socio-economic status and antisocial behaviour.

Good behaviour among students is a fact that comes from acting decently. A person's behaviour is how they act towards other individuals, the society, or things (Kayne, 2022). According to Pavlov (1904), something can be excellent or bad, acceptable or unacceptable, normal or abnormal, and learned or unlearned. Good behaviour has helped students develop morals, values, attitudes, and sensibility—all of which support their intellectual, social, psychological, and spiritual growth. In this study, conduct is defined as an individual's overt or covert actions, and it is evaluated in part by looking at students' disciplinary records.

According to Zubaidia (2019), discipline in schools includes upholding established rules and regulations as well as exhibiting self-control, restraint, and respect for others as well as oneself. According to Ogbonna (2023), discipline occurs when teachers instill in their students a respect for the authority figures in the school, an adherence to the rules and policies, and a maintenance of the expected conduct standards. The driving force behind students adhering to the laws and norms required to fulfil their academic obligations is discipline. It's a factor that prevents students from acting in an antisocial or disruptive manner.

Antisocial behaviour according to Kimberly and Jacob (2022) is any act that imposes physical or psychological harm on other people or their properties. Such acts for them may sometimes constitute a violation of legal codes. Intentional violence and both overt and covert animosity towards other people are other characteristics of this disruptive activity (Clare, 2016). Aggressive acts against property, including theft, vandalism, and lighting fires, are also considered antisocial behaviour. According to Walker et al. (2018), antisocial behaviour is any action that obstructs or interferes with someone's capacity to carry out their legitimate activities. It is a behaviour that both male and female pupils consistently display in violation of socially acceptable behaviour patterns.

According to Clare (2016), antisocial behaviour includes high-risk activities involving self-such as examination malpractice, sexual immorality, juvenile delinquency, smoking, cultism, lateness to assemblies and classes, fighting, aggressive actions against siblings, peers, parents, teachers, like verbal abuse, bullying and hitting, drug abuse and truancy. However, for this study, the researcher will investigate students and teachers' perception of influence of antisocial behaviours in public senior secondary school students' academic performance.

Truancy according to Okwakpam and Okwakpam (2022), is any intentional unauthorized or illegal absence from compulsory schooling. It may also refer to students who attend school but do not go to classes. It is irregular school attendance. Truancy is a delinquent act of staying off from school (Animasahun, 2019). According to Odeomelam and Ajoku (2016), "truancy is a situation where a pupil loiters, wanders, and idles about, gallivants, rigmaroles, walks around, and perambulates while lessons are progressing in the classroom." Children like these can leave home for school and not make it there. Students who engage in this behaviour are more likely to engage in risky behaviours such as drug use in men and unwanted pregnancies in women. Petegem (2017) stated that truancy has been conceptualized as unjustified intentional absence from school. Fogelman and Hibbett (2016) opined that any absence from school without an acceptable reason is truancy and antisocial behaviour. Gabb (2016) is of the view that truant students leave home but do not get to school or escape from school or class to engage in any other activities that catch up with their imaginations. Truancy is a type of deviant behaviour exhibited by some students in schools without formal permission from the school authority. Siziya et al. (2017) in their study

found that truant adolescents had been reported to engage in risky sexual practice, illicit drug use, alcohol drinking, and cigarette smoking. Erinoshio (2018) observed that schools and colleges have lost their sacred roles as formation centers and have become breeding ground for truants, thugs, gangsters, cultists, and drug abusers.

Drugs are used for man's good health and welfare when used appropriately, when it becomes a habit and affect human functioning; it is then termed drug abuse (Anyanwu in Onwuasoanya, 2020). Drug abuse, according to Ajayi and Ayodele (2023), is the wrong use or inappropriate use of chemical substances that are capable of changing the functions of cells in the body. Ajayi and Ekundayo (2020) also saw drug abuse as over-dependence on and misuse of one particular drug with or without a prior medical diagnosis from qualified health practitioners. Ajayi and Ekundayo further identified dangerous drugs like cocaine, Indian hemp (marijuana), morphine, heroin, tobacco, ephedrine, valium five and Chinese capsules as few among the drugs commonly abused by students. In this study, drug-abuse is excessive use of un-prescribed and prescribed drugs to the point that it becomes a habit. In an attempt to control sleep or get energized, most students start experimenting with tobacco, alcohol, ephedrine, and other caffeinated substances such as Nescafe and red bull. Ajayi and Ekundayo stated some of the implications of drug abuse as mental illness, low self-esteem and self-respect, injuries to one's health, increase in crime rate and cultism. Thus, engaging in these antisocial behaviours according to Kimberly and Arriola (2016) pose a great risk to students' mental and physical health in terms of loss of life, low self-esteem, cognitive depression, and disruptions in the teaching and learning process.

These antisocial behaviours no doubt could affect adversely the principals, the teachers, the school facilities, as well as the disciplinary tone of the school and invariably the students' academic achievements in school. Aminu et al. (2015) in their study found that involvement in anti-social behaviour by secondary school students has a significant relationship with their school achievement. Curriculum planners have implemented various measures to eradicate antisocial behaviour in schools. For example, Adeyemo (2021) reports that guidance and counselling services, as well as religious and moral instruction, have been reinstated in schools to instill moral values in students. Regretfully, these strategies and measures don't seem to have had much of an impact on the prevalence of antisocial behaviour in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. For example, some students from a community secondary school in the area were expelled because Indian hemp was found in their school bags by the school authority. Students who exhibit these behaviours may lack concentration in their studies. The question then is "what is the perception of teachers on the effects of antisocial behaviours on Students academic performance of secondary school students?"

Counselling has been used to designate a wide range of procedures comprising advice giving, support in times of trouble or need, encouragement, information giving, and test interpretation. Counselling is a process by which a person is assisted to behave in a more rewarding manner. Counselling is viewed as a personalized, intimate interview or dialogue between a person experiencing some emotional, social, educational, physical, and vocational problems and a professional counsellor. It can also be seen as a service that helps individual to solve problems and learn to cope with these problems that are not easy to solve (Nweze & Okolie, 2023). The central idea of counselling service is mainly the transmission of knowledge, societal values. Counselling service try to curb the negative trend of morality among students in the society, the home and school. According to Barrett, and Olswang, (2014) counselling service as a dynamic and purposeful relationship between two people who approach a mutually defined problem, with mutual consideration of each other to the end that the younger or less mature of the two is aided to a self-determined resolution to his/her problem.

As curriculum implementers, the teachers are always faced with the challenges of helping the students to acquire knowledge and form their character in a rightful direction. They play the role of inculcating the right attitude and manner on students, especially when viewed from the fact that students whom they teach are drawn from different home backgrounds, accommodate the influence of peer groups, and are bound to exhibit different patterns of behaviour that may not conform with the instructional standard of

the school (Adeyemi, 2021). It is important to find out their perception on the effect of truancy and drug abuse on students' academic performance in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State due to the growing rate of poor Academic performance among many of the secondary school students in Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) in the study area.

Statement of the Problem

Secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis in Rivers State, are set up with the objective of preparing young people for higher education and to pursue other vocation or career path. This makes this level of education very important because it determines the quality of workforce that will be released to man various sectors of the economy. Unfortunately, it has been observed that there is declining interest of students towards schooling and worst still is the observed poor attitude to learning among most students in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis attributed to antisocial behaviours of students. In secondary schools, the recurrence of students' antisocial behaviours such as cultism, examination malpractices, sexual permissiveness, alcoholic and drug addiction, lying and dishonesty, disrespect for constituted authority, abortion, truancy, indecent dressing, bullying, rape, lateness, vulgarities and even suicide.

The problem of antisocial behaviours as exhibited by the students has metamorphosed into a cankerworm with devastating consequences both on the students themselves and the Nigeria society at large. This has affected the education system in a very negative way This is the reason why counseling services in the school system has become an important area of focus in the recent time in Rivers State and some other parts of the world. Counselling services need to come to the rescue at this level. The reported poor performance of students in the West African Senior Secondary Examination is a testament of this fact.

These antisocial behaviours of students have been attributed to a number of factors as seen in several studies carried out by other researchers. Some have attributed it to the student's family and peers. A child's behaviour is influenced by parenting practices. Parental involvement in their children's lives, such as providing love, guidance, and support, as well as establishing limits on their behaviour and monitoring what they see or hear, are all beneficial to their growth and development. But when such is absent it results to antisocial externalizing behaviours from the child such as aggression, delinquency and the use of alcohol or other addictive substances. For peers, when a student is rejected by a group of positive peers, they are more likely to engage with a group of negative peers who are also likely to have been rejected. The question then is to what extent does antisocial behaviours influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State? Providing answers through counselling to this question is the problem of this study.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine Students and Teachers' Perception of Influence of Antisocial Behaviours in Public Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State: Implication for Counselling. Specifically, the study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. Determine the extent to which truancy influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.
2. Find out the extent to which drug abuse influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent does truancy influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?
2. To what extent does drug abuse influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of students and teachers on the extent truancy influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of students and teachers on the extent drug abuse influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey design with a population of 27,082 teachers and students comprising 25,077 students and 2,005 teachers in the 38 public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 728 respondents comprising 394 students and 334 teachers in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's formula. The multi-stage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample of the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-designed questionnaire titled "Students and Teachers' Perception of Influence of Antisocial Behaviours in Public Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire". Responses to the questionnaire items were structured on a four- point summated rating scale of: Very High Extent (VHE) – 4points, High Extent (HE) – 3points, Low Extent (LE) – 2points and Very Low Extent (VLE). The questionnaire was validated by experts in Measurement and Evaluation. A test of internal consistency was conducted using Cronbach Alpha method to determine the reliability of the instrument. Reliability coefficients of 0.79, and 0.81 were obtained for the various clusters of the instrument. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation statistics while the hypotheses were tested using z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypotheses accepted when the computed value was greater than the critical value at the significance level of 0.05. On the contrary, the null hypothesis was also accepted and the alternate hypotheses rejected when the computed value is less than the critical table value.

RESULT PRESENTATION

Research Question 1: *To what extent does truancy influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Extent Truancy Influence Public Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance as Perceived by Students and Teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

S/N	Items	Students N= 394		Teachers N=334		Average mean	Std	RMK
		\bar{X}_1	Std ₁	\bar{X}_2	Std ₂			
1.	Staying away from class while lesson is going on in class affects students' academic performance.	3.65	0.89	3.69	0.87	3.67	0.88	HE
2.	Students like discussing with their friends outside the school compound during school hours which affect their academic performance.	4.19	1.33	4.20	1.29	4.19	1.31	HE
3.	Staying away from school affects students' academic performance.	3.00	0.68	3.02	0.67	3.01	0.68	HE
4.	Absenteeism in school affects students' academic performance.	3.07	0.78	3.09	0.78	3.08	0.79	HE
5.	Students prefer hanging around the school orchard with their friends during school hours which affects academic performance.	3.00	0.75	3.03	0.74	3.02	0.75	HE
Aggregate Mean/SD for Students and Teachers		3.38	0.89	3.41	0.87	3.39	0.88	HE

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 1, in response to research question 1 which states to what extent does truancy influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, had the following opinion scores for both students and teachers. With standard deviations of 0.89, 1.33, 0.68, 0.78, and 0.75, the mean scores for students on questionnaire items 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 were 3.65, 4.19, 3.00, 3.07, and 3.00, while the mean scores for teachers were 3.69, 4.20, 3.02, 3.09, and 3.03, with standard deviations of 0.87, 1.29, 0.67, 0.78, and 0.74. In addition, the mean set, which represented the average mean scores for students and teachers, was 3.67, 4.19, 3.01, 3.08, and 3.02; the corresponding standard deviations were 0.88, 1.31, 0.68, 0.79, and 0.75. The readings that are above the 3.00 criteria mean suggested that truancy influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

RQ 2: *To what extent does drug abuse influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?*

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Extent Drug Abuse Influence Public Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance as Perceived by Students and Teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

S/N	Items	Students N= 394		Teachers N=334		Average mean		RMK
		\bar{X}_1	Std1	\bar{X}_2	Std2		Std	
6.	Drug addiction affects students' academic achievement in school.	4.30	1.24	4.36	1.18	4.33	1.21	VHE
7.	Students develop hatred for reading each time they use drug.	4.54	1.02	4.56	1.01	4.55	1.01	VHE
8.	Students' use of drug distorts their thinking patterns which becomes detrimental to academic engagement.	3.48	0.84	3.48	0.81	3.48	0.83	HE
9.	Students who always spend time with their friends smoking instead of reading their books perform very poor academically.	3.52	0.90	3.51	0.87	3.52	0.89	HE
10.	Drug addiction makes some students lack concentration in school.	4.69	0.77	4.71	0.73	4.70	0.75	VHE
Aggregate Mean/SD for Students and Teachers		3.91	0.96	4.12	0.92	4.12	0.94	VHE

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2, in response to research question 2 which states to what extent does drug abuse influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, had the following opinion scores for both students and teachers. Questionnaire items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 yielded mean scores for students of 4.30, 4.54, 3.48, 3.52 and 4.69 with standard deviations of 1.24, 1.02, 0.84, 0.90 and 0.77, and for students of 4.36, 4.56, 3.48, 3.51 and 4.71 with standard deviations of 1.18, 1.01, 0.81, 0.87 and 0.73. Additionally, the average mean scores for students and teachers 4.33, 4.55, 3.48, 3.52, and 4.70 in the mean set, with corresponding standard deviations of 1.21, 1.01, 0.83, 0.89, and 0.75.

The readings that above the 3.00 criteria mean showed that drug abuse influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Hypotheses Testing

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of students and teachers on the extent truancy influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Table 3: Z-test Analysis on the Extent Truancy Influence Public Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance as Perceived by Students and Teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

Respondents	N	x	Std	DF	z-cal	z-crit	LS	Decision
Students	394	3.38	0.89					Accepted
Teachers	334	3.41	0.87	726	0.73	±1.96	0.05	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of students and teachers on the extent drug abuse influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis on the Extent Drug Abuse Influence Public Senior Secondary School Students' Academic Performance as Perceived by Students and Teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.

Respondents	N	x	Std	DF	z-cal	z-crit	LS	Decision
Students	394	3.91	0.96					Accepted
Teachers	334	4.12	0.92	726	0.51	±1.96	0.05	

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

The result on Table 4, above shows Z-test Analysis on the extent Drug abuse influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The table's result indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers and students on the extent Drug abuse influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The table's additional result revealed a z-calculated value of 0.51, which at the 0.05 level of significance and with 726 degrees of freedom was less than the z-critical value of ±1.96. As a consequence, the null hypothesis, which asserts that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers and students on the extent Drug

abuse influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, was accepted.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 1, indicates that Truancy influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. Table 3 result indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of students and teachers on the extent Truancy influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. At the 0.05 level of significance and with 726 degrees of freedom, the table's result revealed a z-calculated value of 0.73, which was less than the z- critical value of 1.96. As a result, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of students and teachers on the extent Truancy influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, was accepted. This finding is in agreement with the earlier findings by Oluremi (2013) who found that truancy affects the academic performance of students. Also, in support of these, Animasahun (2019) stated that truancy influences students' performance in secondary schools. However, the findings of the study are not in line with the earlier findings by Samson (2018) who found out that there is no difference between the academic performance of truant students and non- truant students.

Table 2, Drug abuse influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance as perceived by students and teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. Table 4 additional result revealed a z-calculated value of 0.51, which at the 0.05 level of significance and with 726 degrees of freedom was less than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 . As a consequence, the null hypothesis, which asserts that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers and students on the extent Drug abuse influence public senior secondary school students' academic performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, was accepted. This finding is in agreement with the earlier finding by Abdu-Raheem (2023) who found out that that drug abuse significantly affects students' academic performance in Ekiti and Ondo States. Also, Aminu, Sharehu, Achor, and Onah (2015) opined that drug use and anti-social behaviour indulged in by students are strong indices of poor academic achievement.

Counseling Implications

The findings of a study on the extent to which truancy and drug abuse influences academic performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis have several counseling implications for educators, school counselors, and parents. Below are some of the major implications:

For Truancy

- i. **Early Identification of Truancy:** It is crucial for school counselors and teachers to identify truancy early in order to intervene before it becomes a persistent issue. Regular monitoring of attendance records, combined with teacher observations and student assessments, can help identify students at risk of truancy. Early intervention may involve a one-on-one discussion with the student to understand the reasons behind their absences and to develop strategies to encourage better attendance.
- ii. **Individualized Counseling and Support:** Students engaging in truancy often face personal, emotional, or social issues that contribute to their absenteeism. School counselors should offer individualized counseling sessions to understand the specific challenges that students face. These may include family problems, academic difficulties, peer pressure, or mental health concerns. By providing a safe and confidential space, counselors can help students address underlying issues and develop healthier coping mechanisms.
- iii. **Creating a Supportive School Environment:** School counselors and administrators should work to create an inclusive and supportive school environment that promotes student engagement and reduces the desire to skip school. Programs that enhance school climate, such as anti-bullying

initiatives, peer mentoring, and extracurricular activities, can foster a sense of belonging and make students feel more motivated to attend school regularly.

- iv. Engaging Parents and Caregivers: Truancy is often a reflection of family dynamics or lack of parental involvement. Counseling should extend to parents, helping them understand the importance of regular school attendance and the long-term consequences of truancy on their children's academic success. Parents should be encouraged to engage in open communication with their children about school and provide support at home to address any barriers to attendance.

For Drug -Abuse

- i. Prevention Programs: School counselors should implement drug prevention programs that educate students about the dangers of substance abuse and its impact on academic performance. These programs should provide students with alternatives to drug use, such as engaging in extracurricular activities, sports, or hobbies that foster academic success and emotional well-being.
- ii. Early Identification and Intervention: Teachers and school counselors should be trained to identify early signs of drug abuse among students. This may include physical signs (such as bloodshot eyes, changes in appetite), behavioral indicators (withdrawal, aggression), and academic signs (decline in grades, lack of focus). Early identification allows for prompt intervention, which may include counseling sessions, referral to rehabilitation programs, or parental involvement.
- iii. Personal and Academic Counseling: Students struggling with drug abuse require both personal and academic counseling. Counselors should address the emotional, psychological, and social factors that may contribute to substance abuse, such as peer pressure, stress, or family issues. In parallel, counselors should work with students to set academic goals, improve study habits, and provide strategies for managing time and stress effectively.
- iv. Parental Involvement: Parents play a crucial role in combating drug abuse and its academic consequences. Counseling sessions for parents should focus on building awareness about drug abuse, signs to watch for, and ways to provide support for their children. Parents should also be encouraged to create a supportive home environment that emphasizes the importance of education and personal well-being.

CONCLUSION

From the result of the study on students and teachers' perception of influence of antisocial behaviours in public senior secondary school students' academic performance in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. Counselling services in secondary schools make provision of values amongst the individuals which tend to disseminate healthy, behaviours and interactions amongst the students and other persons in the environment. These values include, courtesy, decorum, responsibility, integrity, honesty, humility and team spirit. Counselling focuses on in-depth discussion of problems and sharing information that aids understanding and future decision making and eliminate anti-social behavior among students. There is a need for parents to put more effort to ensure that their children are adequately provided for and morally groomed.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that:

1. There is a need for collaboration between teachers and parents to stem the tide of truancy and drug abuse to enhance the academic performance of students in public secondary school.
2. The result highlights the need for enlightenment campaigns by government agencies and non-government organizations for parents and children on the dangers inherent in truancy and drug abuse.

3. There is also a need for an education monitoring agency that will be visiting various schools at the Local, State, and Federal Government levels to checkmate issues of anti-social behaviours especially truancy and drug abuse in Nigerian secondary schools. Hence, more effort should be made to develop truancy and drug abuse prevention strategies in secondary schools.
4. Parents and school administrators must work together to keep students' behaviour under effective control, as many of the causes of anti-social behaviour can be traced to schools, homes, and peer influence, to name just a few.

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